

Application of the Finite Element Method to Determine the Moisture Content of Composites under Transient Conditions

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ABSTRACT

The transient diffusion equations of the type encountered in moisture content analysis of composite materials are formulated in terms of the finite element method. Curved three-dimensional isoparametric elements are used in a time-marching solution. The analogy between the governing field equations used for moisture content analysis and the equations for the heat conduction analysis is discussed. It is shown that the moisture content of composites can be computed using existing finite element heat conduction computer programs with some modifications. The accuracy of the method is illustrated by means of several examples using the WECAN finite element general purpose structural analysis computer program.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of composite materials may be adversely affected when such materials are exposed to high humidity environments for long periods of time. In order to utilize the full potential of composite materials, it is important to know their response to these moist environments. A theory to determine the moisture content of composites under such conditions was presented by Shen and Springer [1]. They presented a closed form solution for a one dimensional single material system using Fick's second law of diffusion. An extension of this theory to analyze multi-material systems was given by Miller [2]. The objective of this investigation is to search for a more general approach to determine the moisture content within complex structures of arbitrary shape used in practical design. To meet this objective, the transient diffusion equations of the type encountered in moisture content analysis of composite material is formulated in terms of the finite element method. Finite element technology is used extensively for structural analysis and has also been applied in other engineering analyses [3]. It is concluded that the time-dependent moisture content of composites can be determined using existing general purpose finite element heat conduction computer programs with some modifications.

GOVERNING EQUATION

The moisture content of composite materials is assumed to be governed by

Fick's second law in diffusion [1, 4].

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (D_x \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (D_y \frac{\partial C}{\partial y}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (D_z \frac{\partial C}{\partial z}) - \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$C(0) = C_0$$

subject to boundary conditions

$$C = C_A \text{ on surface A (see Fig. 1).}$$

and

$$D_x \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} l_x + D_y \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} l_y + D_z \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} l_z + q = 0 \text{ on surface B} \quad (2)$$

where C is moisture concentration; D_x , D_y and D_z are diffusivities in the x , y and z axes, respectively; l_x , l_y and l_z are direction cosines of the vector normal to the surface B; and q is the moisture input per unit area.

Let the unknown moisture concentration C through the solution domain be approximated as:

$$C = \sum N_i(x, y, z) C_i(t) \quad (3)$$

where N_i 's are the shape functions defined piecewise and $C_i(t)$'s are the moisture concentrations at node i .

Following the well-known Galerkin approach [5], equations (1), (2) and (3) can be written in a matrix form:

$$[H] \{C\} + [B] \{C\} + \{F\} = 0 \quad (4a)$$

$$\{C(0)\} = \{C_0\}$$

in which

$$H_{ij} = \sum \int_V (-\frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x} D_x \frac{\partial N_j}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial y} D_y \frac{\partial N_j}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial z} D_z \frac{\partial N_j}{\partial z}) dV \quad (4b)$$

where the summation covers the contribution of all elements involved and v is the volume of the corresponding element.

$$B_{ij} = \sum \int_V N_i N_j dV \quad (4c)$$

$$F_i = \sum \int_S N_i q dS$$

where S applies only to elements with an external surface.

The above form is valid for all types of elements and more detailed derivation for three-dimensional curved isoparametric elements will be formulated in the next section.

ELEMENT FORMULATION

Consider a curved three-dimensional hexahedron element as shown in Fig. 2. If we write

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \sum N_i x_i \\ y &= \sum N_i y_i \\ z &= \sum N_i z_i \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

in which N_i 's are shape functions given in terms of the local coordinates α , β and γ which have values of ± 1 on opposite faces and x_i , y_i and z_i are coordinates of node i , then the distribution of moisture content within the element is expressed as:

$$C = \sum N_i C_i \quad (6)$$

To derive the matrix [H] and the vector {F} in the Cartesian coordinate system, a few transformations are needed. The derivative components transform as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial z} \end{Bmatrix} = [J]^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial \alpha} \\ \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial \beta} \\ \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial \gamma} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where [J] is the Jacobian in the following form

$$[J] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \alpha} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \alpha} & \frac{\partial z}{\partial \alpha} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \beta} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \beta} & \frac{\partial z}{\partial \beta} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \gamma} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \gamma} & \frac{\partial z}{\partial \gamma} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The volume of elements becomes

$$dx \, dy \, dz = \det [J] \, d\alpha \, d\beta \, d\gamma \quad (9)$$

Substituting equations (7), (8) and (9) into equations (4b) and (4c), the matrices can be evaluated by numerical integration [6].

The element matrices for two-dimensional isoparametric elements as shown in Fig. 3 can be obtained with similar procedures. It is interesting to note that with careful choice of the shape function within the computer program, one can vary the number of side nodes as shown in Fig. 3d.

TIME-MARCHING SCHEME

Governing equation (4a) is a system of first-order linear differential equations and a numerical recurrence process is required to find the solution at subsequent times. In this study the generalized Crank-Nicholson-Galerkin integration scheme [7,8] is adopted. This recurrence equation has the following form:

$$[\delta[H] + \frac{1}{\Delta t} [B]] \{C_{n+1}\} = \{F_{n+1}\} + [(\delta - 1) [H] + \frac{1}{\Delta t} [B]] \{C_n\} \quad (10)$$

where δ is a constant. When $\delta = 1/2$, equation (10) represents the Crank-Nicholson recurrence formula; if $\delta = 2/3$, equation (10) becomes the Galerkin process with linear interpolation [8]. By experience $\delta = 2/3$ has been found to give the best convergence properties for many practical applications.

ANALOGY BETWEEN MOISTURE CONTENT ANALYSIS AND HEAT CONDUCTION ANALYSIS

The governing equations used for the moisture content analysis are identical to those used for the heat conduction analysis if the analogies shown in Table 1 are drawn. The main difference between the moisture content analysis and the heat conduction analysis is that the diffusivity is very sensitive to

the temperature. Therefore, two separate runs are required to complete the analysis if the composite body to be analyzed is not at uniform temperature. In the first run, the temperature distribution can be obtained by using the conventional finite element heat conduction analysis. In the second run, the moisture content analysis can be accomplished using the same procedures as those of the first run except that the material constants need to be modified according to Table 1. To perform the analysis, the computer program must provide the following additional capabilities:

1. To include the effects of material anisotropy.
2. To have the capability to retrieve the temperature distribution obtained in the first run and then calculate the diffusivity accordingly.
3. To include the capability to calculate the weight gained during the process of moisture absorption.

Experience has indicated that those capabilities can be implemented into an existing general purpose heat conduction finite element analysis computer program with a minimum of effort.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Two examples will be analyzed using the heat conduction capability of the WECAN [7] finite element structural analysis computer program developed jointly by Westinghouse Research & Development Center and Westinghouse Nuclear Energy Systems. The accuracy of the results are verified by comparing them with known solutions. It should be noted that although both examples demonstrated here are one-dimensional in nature, the method can also be applied to both two-dimensional and three-dimensional problems.

Example 1

A thick composite plate as shown in Fig. 4 is exposed to moisture concentration C_m on both sides; the initial moisture content is assumed to be C_0 . Due to its symmetry and the one-dimensional nature of this problem, only the shaded area as shown in Fig. 4 is modeled. Five mixed cubic elements as shown in Fig. 4 are used. The resulting time history of the moisture concentration at a few selected points are plotted and compared with those of the analytical solution [1] in Fig. 5.

Example 2

A two-material system exposed to constant humidity and constant temperature is shown in Fig. 6. Due to symmetry, only the shaded area as shown in Fig. 6 is modeled. Six mixed cubic elements as shown in Fig. 6 are used. The moisture content distribution at a few selected times are plotted in Fig. 7 and their behavior agrees with those of Miller [2]. The results satisfy the condition of equilibrium of moisture crossing the surfaces of two adjacent layers per unit area and unit time [9], i.e.,

$$\left[D_x \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right]_{\text{left layer}} = \left[D_x \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right]_{\text{right layer}}$$

CONCLUSIONS

As a result of the analogy between the governing equations used for moisture content analysis and those used for heat conduction analysis, the moisture content of composites can be analyzed using existing finite element heat conduction computer programs with some modifications. Experience has indicated that these modifications can be implemented into an existing general purpose heat conduction finite element analysis computer program with a minimum of effort.

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TABLE 1

ANALOGY BETWEEN HEAT CONDUCTION ANALYSIS AND
MOISTURE CONTENT ANALYSIS

C - Moisture Concentration	T - Temperature
D_x, D_y and D_z - Diffusivity	K_x, K_y and K_z - Conductivity
q - Moisture input at the boundary	q - Heat input at the boundary
1 - Unity	pc - Heat capacity

Fig. 1-A three dimensional body

Fig. 2—A three-dimensional isoparametric element

a) Linear Element

b) Quadratic Element

c) Cubic Element

d) Mixed Element

Fig. 3—Two-dimensional isoparametric element

Fig. 4—Composite plate subject to moisture at both sides

Fig. 5—Time-history of moisture concentration

Fig. 6—A two-material system exposed to constant humidity and temperature

Fig. 7—Moisture content distribution of a Boron/Graphite/Boron material system exposed to constant moisture and constant temperature